

VoQS: 音质符号 Voice Quality Symbols

气流类型 Airstream Types

Ⓓ 颊气流 buccal airstream	↓ 肺部吸气言语 pulmonic ingressive speech
Ⓔ 食管气流 oesophageal airstream	IO 气管-食管言语 tracheo-oesophageal speech

发声类型 Phonation Types

V 常态浊声 modal voice	F 假声 falsetto	W 耳语 whisper	C 嘎裂 creak
V̥ 耳语声 whispery voice	V̥ 嘎裂声 creaky voice	V̥ 气声 breathy voice	V! 糙声 harsh voice
F̥ 耳语假声 whispery falsetto	F̥ 嘎裂假声 creaky falsetto	C! 糙嘎裂 harsh creak	
F! 糙假声 harsh falsetto	C! 糙嘎裂 harsh creak	V! 糙嘎裂声 harsh creaky voice	
V! 糙耳语声 harsh whispery voice	V! 糙嘎裂声 harsh creaky voice	V! 糙耳语嘎裂声 harsh whispery creaky voice	
V̥ 耳语嘎裂声 whispery creaky voice	V̥ 耳语嘎裂声 whispery creaky voice	V! 糙耳语嘎裂声 harsh whispery creaky voice	
F̥ 耳语嘎裂假声 whispery creaky falsetto	F̥ 耳语嘎裂假声 whispery creaky falsetto	F! 糙耳语嘎裂假声 harsh whispery creaky falsetto	
V̥ 弛/松声 slack/lax voice	V̥ 挤喉发声/紧声 pressed phonation / tight voice	V!! 复音 diplophonia	
V!! 室襞性发声 ventricular phonation	V!! 复音 diplophonia	V ^{AA} 杓状会厌襞性发声 aryepiglottic phonation	
V!! 耳语室襞性发声 whispery ventricular phonation	V ^{AA} 杓状会厌襞性发声 aryepiglottic phonation	II 电子喉发声 electrolarynx phonation	
ΛV 痉挛性发声障碍 spasmodic dysphonia	II 电子喉发声 electrolarynx phonation		

喉位高度 Larynx Height

L̥ 喉位偏高声 raised-larynx voice	L̥ 喉位偏低声 lowered-larynx voice
------------------------------	-------------------------------

喉上形态 Supralaryngeal Settings

唇部形态、舌部形态、软腭状态、颌和舌的形态

Labial settings, lingual settings, state of the velum, jaw and tongue settings

V ^o 唇化声 (开圆唇) labialized voice (open rounded)	V ^w 唇化声 (闭圆唇) labialized voice (close rounded)
V̥ 展唇声 spread-lip voice	V ^u 唇齿化声 labio-dentalized voice
V̥ 舌尖化声 linguo-apicalized voice	V̥ 舌叶化声 linguo-laminalized voice
V̥ 卷舌声 retroflex voice	V̥ 齿化声 dentalized voice
V̥ 龈化声 alveolarized voice	V̥ ^j 腭-龈化声 palato-alveolarized voice
V̥ ^j 腭化声 palatalized voice	V ^v 软腭化声 velarized voice
V ^ɸ 小舌化声 uvularized voice	V ^s 咽化声 pharyngealized voice
V ^s 喉-咽化声 laryngo-pharyngealized voice	V ^H 咽门化声 faucalized voice
Ṽ 鼻化声 nasalized voice	Ṽ 去鼻化声 denasalized voice
J̥ 颌位偏开声 open-jaw voice	J̥ 颌位偏闭声 close-jaw voice
J̥ 颌位偏右声 right offset-jaw voice	J̥ 颌位偏左声 left offset-jaw voice
J̥ 颌位突出声 protruded-jaw voice	⊖ 舌突出声 protruded-tongue voice

带标签的大括号和数字用来标记音质的等级和组合:

Labeled braces and numerals mark degree and combinations of voice quality:

[^h nɔ̃ məl 'vɔɪs {3V! 'vɛɪ 'hɑ̃} 'vɔɪs 3V!} {L̥ 1V! 'les 'hɑ̃} 'vɔɪs wɪð 'ɔɪz d 'læɪŋks 1V! L̥}]
--